

Appendix 6.2: Responses to transboundary environmental challenges within the Europe and Central Asia region (Chapter 6, Section 6.3.3)

Table 6.2.1 shows a number of bilateral agreements between Mongolia, Russia and China related to water management and nature conservation relevant to transboundary Amur River basin.

Table 6.2.1: Bilateral water and nature conservation agreements between Mongolia, Russia and China

	Title	Description
1956	Sino-Soviet Agreement on development of "Grand Amur Scheme"	Agreement between the USSR and China on joint research operations on planning and survey operations to prepare a scheme for the multi-purpose exploitation of the Argun River and the Upper Amur River.
1986	Sino-Russian Agreement on development of "Joint Comprehensive Scheme for Water Management on Amur and Argun Rivers"	Bilateral overview of developments planned by the water and energy authorities of China and Russia led by the Song-Liao Water Resource Commission of China and Sovintervod Hydro-engineering Institute of USSR Water Resources Ministry.
1994	Mongolia-China – Agreement on Use and Protection of Transboundary Waters	Agreement on the protection and utilization of transboundary waters including aquatic biota
1994	Russia-China Agreement on protection of aquatic bio-resources in transboundary Amur- and Ussuri Rivers	Protects 25 fishes, two crustaceans, one turtle, one mollusk, three aquatic plants. Regulates size limits for fish, net mesh sizes and lengths, seasonal fishing bans, closure of waters to fishing, and permitted fishing gear. Does not cover Argun river and Khanka Lake.
1994	Agreement on Dauria International Protected Area	Trilateral agreement was signed by China, Mongolia, and Russia to establish Dauria International Protected Area (DIPA) to protect globally important grasslands in the headwaters of the Amur-Heilong basin. Includes three biosphere reserves with Ramsar wetlands.
1994	Russia-China Cooperation in Protection of the Natural Environment	Governed by Task Force on Environmental Protection should have met annually, but was stalled. This non-effective mechanism was succeeded by Environmental Sub-commission under the Commission on Regular Meetings of Heads of State in 2006.
1995	Russia-Mongolia - Agreement on Use and Protection of Transboundary Waters	Agreement between the government of Mongolia and the government of the Russian Federation on the protection and use of transboundary waters. Replaced much more detailed and binding agreement "On Selenge river Basin water resources management"
1996	Russia-China Agreement on Khanka/Xingkai Lake International Nature Reserve	The agreement envisioned a broad range of cooperative activities and established a "Mixed Chinese-Russian Commission on Lake Khanka/Xingkai International Nature Reserve". Commission was formed only in March 2009, but cooperation between nature reserves started from 2003.
2002	Russia-China Treaty on good neighbor relations, friendship and cooperation	Has chapter on cooperative development of the border region with a clause on protection and improvement of the natural environment and just and equitable management of transboundary rivers.
2006	Sino-Russian Environmental Sub-commission under the Commission on Regular Meetings of Heads of State	Highest level commission coordinated by MNR in Russia and Effectively replaced mechanisms set under 1994 environmental agreement. Meets annually. Has three task forces on: "green issues" – biodiversity, protected areas, ecosystem conservation, etc.; pollution prevention and cooperation in case of environmental emergencies; protection of transboundary waters and monitoring of water quality"

2006	Sino-Russian protocol on "common approaches to monitoring of transboundary waters"	2006 a special protocol on "common approaches to monitoring of transboundary waters" was signed between SEPA and MNR. It calls for the establishment of two working groups for planning and coordinating water quality monitoring in transboundary rivers: Amur-Heilong, Ussuri-Wusuli, Argun and Razdolnaya (Suifen).
2008	Sino-Russian Agreement on Use and Protection of Transboundary Waters	Framework agreement that sets mechanism for consultations and information exchange. Joint Commission is governed by Ministry of Foreign Relations, MEP and Ministry of Water resources from China side and MNR from Russia side. In January 2014 the 6th meeting of China-Russia Transboundary Water Joint Commission tasked its Working Group on Water Resources Management to conduct research and produce a Joint Report on 2013 flood on Amur River.
2011	Sino-Russian strategy for development of transboundary protected area network in Amur River basin"	Rationale for cooperation: "as economic cooperation in border areas increase, the pressures and threats to biodiversity may also increase and therefore more active and comprehensive cooperation in nature conservation is needed." The Strategy envisions cooperation on 12 aspects of transboundary ecosystem conservation, including: biodiversity inventories, ecological monitoring, evaluation of management performance, protected areas planning, information sharing, enforcement measures, joint research, mutual training and public education efforts.
2014	Intergovernmental memorandum of intent on flood management cooperation	Signed by Russian Ministry of Emergencies and PRC Ministry of Water Resources. Joint Sino-Russian Group for Flood Fighting was formed and since held annual meetings.

Source: Simonov & Egidarev (2017).

A selection of key conventions aimed at fostering transboundary marine protection in Europe and Central Asia is displayed in **Table 6.2.2**. The table describes the geographical scope, and responsible entities for respective convention.

Table 6.2.2: Transboundary Conventions for marine protection

Transboundary marine policy area	Instrument	Responsible entity	Description
Global	UNESCO's – marine spatial planning	UNESCO	Initiative that assists countries operationalise ecosystem-based management by finding space for biodiversity conservation and sustainable economic development in marine environments through marine spatial planning.
Baltic Sea	Helsinki Convention	HELCOM	Convention on the Protection of the Marine Environment of the Baltic Sea Area.
North East Atlantic	OSPAR Convention	OSPAR	Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the North-East Atlantic. It focuses on the application of the ecosystem approach to the management of human activities in the Northeast Atlantic marine environment and on implementing the precautionary principle, the polluter pays principle and best environmental practices, into marine environmental policy.
Black Sea	The Bucharest Convention	Black Sea Commission	The basic objective of the Convention is to prevent, reduce and control the pollution in the Black Sea in order to protect and preserve the marine environment and to provide legal framework for co-operation and concerted actions to fulfil this obligation.”
Mediterranean	The Barcelona Convention	The Barcelona Convention	The convention provides seven protocols to address specific aspects of Mediterranean environmental conservation including marine biological diversity and pollution from exploration and exploitation offshore.
Aral Sea	Agreement on joint activities in addressing the Aral Sea crisis (and surroundings) improving the environment, and ensuring the social and economic development of the Aral Sea region (1993)	Aral Sea Agreement	Concerned with the conservation of land and water resources of the Aral Sea Basin
Caspian Sea	Tehran Convention	Tehran Convention	Framework Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the Caspian Sea was the first legally binding regional agreement signed by all five Caspian littoral States (Azerbaijan, I.R. Iran, Kazakhstan, Russian Federation and Turkmenistan), laying down the general requirements and the institutional mechanisms for marine environmental protection in the Caspian region.
ROPME Sea Area (RSA) extends from the Arabian Gulf to the	ROPME (Regional Organisation for the Protection of the Marine Environment)	Kuwait Convention for the Protection and	The basic legal instrument binding a number of Arabian states to coordinate activities towards the protection of their common marine environment.

Arabian Sea coast of Oman		Development of the Marine Environment and Coastal Areas	
Global	Ramsar Convention	Ramsar Convention	International treaty for the conservation and sustainable use of wetlands

Source: Own representation.